

Do cooking process influences the metal contents in crab and prawn?

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Abstract

Two common shellfish species *Penaeus monodon* (tiger prawn) and *Scylla olivacea* (orange mud crab) were analysed for Zn, Cu, Pb and Cd. For each species, two composite samples were prepared for metal analyses, whose levels in raw and cooked (boiled, steamed, fried and curry) samples were determined by Perkin-Elmer Sciex ELAN 5000 ICP mass spectrometer and expressed as ppm dry weight. The heavy metal content in all shellfish species decreased on cooking (except for lead in shellfish curry). In shellfish curry the concentration of Pb increased significantly. In conclusion it can be advocated that the cooking process greatly influences the metal concentrations in the selected shellfish species.

Keywords: Shellfish, Heavy metals, ICP mass spectrometer, Tiger prawn, Orange mud crab.

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1. Introduction

Shellfish has long been a lucrative food item of people living in the Indian sub-continent, particularly in the Gangetic plain region. During the past 20 years, there has been renewed interest in dietary components such as fish, which are rich sources of omega-3 fatty acids, and might favourably improve lipid profiles and reduce risk of coronary heart disease [1]. Additional reported benefits of fish consumption also include their hypolipidemic and/or anti-atherogenic effects [2], decreased risk of prostate cancer [3] reduced occurrence of renal cell carcinoma in women [4], reduced risk of dementia and alzheimer disease in certain conditions [5]. Although fish is a good source of some essential nutrients, cooking practices could cause modifications in proximate composition, fatty acids and amino acids as well as changes in solubility and nutritional quality of fish [6, 7]. Cooking process can also lead to alteration of heavy metal concentrations and thus influence the physiological system of human beings. Of the heavy metals lead and cadmium are potentially toxic; exposure to these metals can cause renal disturbances and neurological alterations [8]. Although reports are available on the heavy metal concentrations in finfish and shellfish of the lower Gangetic delta [9,10], studies to assess the effect of cooking process on the metal concentrations in fish are very limited. This paper is therefore, an attempt to assess the heavy metal concentrations of cooked shellfishes (tiger prawn and crab) commonly consumed in the Gangetic plain region of India.

2. Materials and Methods

2.1. Sample preparation

Two common shellfish species *Penaeus monodon* (tiger prawn) and *Scylla olivacea* (orange mud crab) were caught during high tide condition from the lower stretch of the mighty River Ganga (22°00'26.07" N and 88°03'29.64" E) during a field trip from 20th

July to 28th July, 2019 (Figures 1 and 2). The collection site (Haldia) is noted for intense industrial and port activities and is basically an industrial HUB in the northeast coast of India. The collected samples were stored in a container, preserved in crushed ice, and brought to the laboratory for further analysis. Similar sized specimens of each species were sorted out for analyzing the metal level in the muscle of shellfishes. About 100 gm of each type of shellfish were sorted out and cleaned by scaling and gutting. They were washed with double distilled water and were subsequently cooked in different ways (Table 1). After the cooking process, the muscles were again washed with double distilled water and oven dried at 80°C overnight to remove the moisture content. 20 mg sample of each species processed in different ways were finally considered for further analysis.

Figure 1: *Penaeus monodon* (tiger prawn) (Source: Mitra [11]).

Figure 2: *Scylla olivacea* (orange mud crab) (Source: Mitra [11])

Table 1: Cooking process adopted in the present study with ingredients

Species	Cooking process	Sample size (gm)	Oil used (ml)	Water used (ml)	Cooking time (min)
<i>Penaeus monodon</i>	Boiled	100	-	250	15
	Steamed	100	-	75	20
	Fried	100	200	-	5
	Curry*	100	50	60	10
<i>Scylla olivacea</i>	Boiled	100	-	250	15
	Steamed	100	-	75	30
	Fried	100	200	-	5
	Curry*	100	50	60	10

* Spice containing mainly turmeric powder, ginger powder, chilli powder, yellow mustard was used

2.2. Analysis

Inductively Coupled Plasma – Mass Spectrometry (ICP-MS) is now - a - day accepted as a fast, reliable means of multi-elemental analysis for a wide variety of sample types [12]. A Perkin-Elmer Sciex ELAN 5000 ICP mass spectrometer was used for the present analysis. A standard torch for this instrument was used with an outer argon gas flow rate of 15 L/min and an intermediate gas flow of 0.9 L/min. The applied power was 1.0 kW. The ion settings were standard settings recommended, when a conventional nebulizer/spray is used with a liquid sample uptake rate of 1.0 mL/min. A Moulinex Super Crouty microwave oven of 2450 MHz frequency magnetron and 1100 Watt maximum power Polytetrafluoroethylene (PTFE) reactor of 115 ml volume, 1 cm wall thickness with hermetic screw caps, were used for the digestion of the collected biological samples. All reagents used were of high purity available and of analytical reagent grade. High purity water was obtained with a Barnstead Nanopure II water-purification system. All glasswares were soaked in 10% (v/v) nitric acid for 24 h and washed with deionised water prior to use.

20 mg composite sample of each species of shellfish cooked in different methods were weighed and successively treated with 4 ml aqua regia, 1.5 mL HF and 3 ml H₂O₂ in a hermetically sealed PIFE reactor, inside a microwave oven, at power levels between 330-550 Watt, for 12 min to obtain a clear solution. The use of microwave-assisted digestion appears to be very relevant for sample dissolution, especially because it is very fast [13-15]. After digestion, 4 ml H₂BO₃ was added and kept in a hot water bath for 10 min, diluted with distilled water to make up the volume to 50 ml. Taking distilled water in place of biological samples and following all the treatment steps described above the blank process was prepared. The final volume was made up to 50 ml. Finally, the samples and process blank solutions were analyzed by ICP-MS. All analyses were done in triplicate and the results were expressed with standard deviation.

The accuracy and precision of our results were checked by analyzing standard reference material (SRM, Dorm-2). The results indicated good agreement between the certified and the analytical values (Table 2).

Table 2: Concentrations of metals found in Standard Reference Material DORM-2 (dogfish muscle) from the National Research Council, Canada (all data as means ± standard errors, in ppm dry wt)

Value	Zn	Cu	Pb	Cd
Certified	26.8	2.34	0.065	0.043
SE	2.41	0.18	0.009	0.005
Observed*	23.9	2.29	0.060	0.040
SE	1.99	0.17	0.006	0.006
Recovery (%)	89.2	97.8	92.3	93.0

*Each value is the average of 5 determinations

3. Results and Discussion

3.1. Heavy metals in shellfish

In the selected shellfish species the metal accumulated as per the order Zn > Cu > Pb > Cd. The species wise accumulation is *Scylla olivacea* > *Penaeus monodon* for all the selected metals in the present study. Romeo *et al* [16] pointed out that the affiance of metal uptake from contaminated water and food may differ in relation to ecological needs, metabolism, and the contamination gradients of water, food and sediment, as well as other factors, such a salinity, temperature and interacting agents. The selected shellfish species in the present study have different food preference and different behavioral pattern.

3.2. Heavy metals in prawn and crab (raw condition)

Zn being an essential element for normal growth and metabolism of animals, exhibited highest accumulation in the shellfish muscle when compared with the other three metals. The values of Zn in tiger prawn and crab are 368.73 and 421.02 ppm dry wt. respectively, much above the limit of WHO (World Health Organization) [17].

Levels of Copper in tiger prawn and crab are 114.71 and 149.81 ppm dry wt. respectively.

The level of Cu is higher than the recommended value of Cu in food, which is 30 ppm as prescribed by WHO [17] (Tables 3 and 4).

High concentration of Pb was observed in tiger prawn muscle freshly caught from the lower stretch of the River Ganga. This may be attributed to intense industrial activities in this region [11, 18, 19]. When compared with the recommended value of WHO [20] in context to consumption of shrimp as food (2 ppm for Pb), the concentrations in all the shrimp species were much above this level (Table 5).

Higher concentrations of Cd were observed in both the prawn and crab, and they were much above the recommended level of WHO [17] (Table 6).

3.3. Cooking effect

Heat treatment by boiling, steaming, frying and curry preparation of fish led to a decrease of the heavy metal content in the muscle of all the shellfish species excepting Pb in curry (Tables 3-6). Metal levels in the shellfish muscle decreased appreciably during steaming than that detected after the boiling process. This may be attributed to the role of latent heat of vaporization in steam unlike boiling water at 100°C. Steam has thus more heat energy (539.6 cal/gm additional) that can denature the protein and breaks its association with the heavy metals. The reduction in the metal contents of the fish during cooking may be related to the release of these metals with the loss of water as free salts, possibly in association with soluble amino acids and uncoagulated proteins [21]. Howarth and Sprague [22] found that the cooking process decreased the protein content of the fish parts; hence, heavy metals that usually bind with proteins also decreased. However in the shellfish curry the Pb concentrations increased significantly. This increase in heavy metal could be due to the ingredients used in cooking, and, recent studies indicate that spices could contain high levels of lead due to contamination [23]. The process of cooking thus plays a major role in altering the concentrations of heavy metals.

The alteration depends on cooking conditions (time, temperature and medium of cooking). Therefore, it is possible to reduce the metal in fish parts by choosing a suitable method of cooking. Our findings (Tables 3-6) reveal that heat energy is the key player in dissociation of heavy metals from the proteins of fish,

which is maximum in steam owing to latent heat of vaporization. Hence in conclusion it can be advocated that contaminated fishes may be consumed after steaming edible parts (like muscle) with water.

Table 3: Zn concentrations (in ppm dry wt.) in shellfish muscles

Species	Raw fish	Boiled fish	Steamed fish	Fried fish	Fish curry
<i>Penaeus monodon</i>	368.73	313.93	202.43	326.43	456.31
<i>Scylla olivacea</i>	421.02	358.255	238.09	371.17	409.32

WHO [17] level for Zn in food: 100 ppm.

Table 4: Cu concentrations (in ppm dry wt.) in shellfish muscles

Species	Raw fish	Boiled fish	Steamed fish	Fried fish	Fish curry
<i>Penaeus monodon</i>	114.71	100.25	88.84	101.00	112.21
<i>Scylla olivacea</i>	149.81	123.57	106.11	124.93	137.54

WHO [17] level for Cu in food: 30 ppm.

Table 5: Pb concentrations (in ppm dry wt.) in shellfish muscles

Species	Raw fish	Boiled fish	Steamed fish	Fried fish	Fish curry
<i>Penaeus monodon</i>	13.01	10.23	7.99	10.89	13.89
<i>Scylla olivacea</i>	12.93	9.83	7.35	10.12	13.24

WHO [17] level for Pb in food: 2 ppm.

Table 6: Cd concentrations (in ppm dry wt.) in shellfish muscles

Species	Raw fish	Boiled fish	Steamed fish	Fried fish	Fish curry
<i>Penaeus monodon</i>	2.11 ± 0.29	1.25	1.00	1.61	2.01
<i>Scylla olivacea</i>	4.43 ± 0.80	2.40	2.02	3.27	4.27

WHO [17] level for Cd in food: 1 ppm.

5. Conclusion

Shrimps and crabs are delicious food items in the Indian sub-continent and are the major exportable items of the country. However, accumulation of heavy metals may lead to health hazard and reject the export of the shellfish from the quality point of view. Hence the present study was conducted to evaluate the quality of tiger prawn and orange crab in terms of heavy metals. The shellfishes were also cooked in different processes to detect any change in the metal levels, and interestingly it was observed that steamed fishes are much safer for consumption than raw, boiled, fried and curries prepared from the selected shellfish species.

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